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SEHRENE

Store Electricity and Heat for climate Neutral Europe

Grant agreement Nr 101135763

Deliverable D1.2

Data Management Plan

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Reviewer	Date	Reviewer Name (Short Organisation Name)
Work Package leader	29/03/2024	Stéphane COLASSON (CEA)
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work Package
ORD	Open Research Data

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Executive Summary

The preparation of this document is linked to the participation of the SEHRENE project in the Open Research Data Pilot, a feature of Horizon Europe. The aim of this document is to describe the data management life cycle for the data sets that will be collected, processed, or generated by the project. It specifies what data will be generated and what methodology and standards will be followed, whether and how the data will be exploited and/or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how they will be archived and preserved. For all those data that will not be publicly disclosed, the explanation is provided.

Nevertheless, it is necessary to mention that the disclosure of the project's data should never jeopardize SEHRENE's main objectives. The protection of generated intellectual property, the confidentiality obligations, and the obligations to protect personal data will always be considered before making the data openly accessible

About the project

SEHRENE project aims to design a new electrothermal energy storage (ETES) concept to store renewable electricity (RE) and heat and to reconstitute it as needed. It is very energy-efficient (80-85%), is geographically independent and uses no critical raw materials. It enables 8-12 times longer storage duration than Li-ion, with LCOS of 80 – 137 €/MWh, depending on the use-case. This is lower than pumped hydro, the lowest-cost commercial electricity storage. Its lifetime of 20-30 years is 2 – 3x longer than Li-ion. A TRL4 prototype and the digital twins of 3 full use-cases will be delivered: (i) ceramics plant storing excess, on-site PV power in a micro-grid and industrial waste-heat for continuous green H₂ production and selfconsumption, (ii) a smart-grid, and (iii) a geothermal power plant. The ETES integrates: (i) a novel heat-pump design with a coefficient of performance of 50% the theoretical maximum, (ii) a novel thermal energy storage system with energy density of 90 kWh/m³ (+30%), containing phase-change material in a novel metallic Kelvin cells-like foam and (iii) ORC with novel operating parameters. New digital tools will optimise the energy management of the storage and facilitate investment decisions by potential end-users taking LCA and technico-economic factors into account. The exploitation plan aims to implement the solution in the first factory in 2029. SEHRENE's market penetration will enable to capture 1% of the market by 2040 avoiding 90Mm³ of NG and 15Mt CO₂/year. R&D and industrial partners project to generate 5.8M€ in revenues by 2035 from sales of heat pumps, thermal storage, ORC, licenses to R&D results and consulting services.

1. Introduction

The current deliverable is part of the Task 1.2 Operational Management. The preparation of this document is linked to the project's participation in the Open Research Data Pilot in the frame of Horizon Europe. The purpose of the document is to describe the data management life cycle for the data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by the SEHRENE project. It specifies which data will be generated, which methodology and standards will be followed, whether and how the data will be exploited and/or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how they will be curated and preserved. For all those data that will not be publicly disclosed, the Data Management Plan (DMP) will provide an explanation for it.

The DMP has been developed in line with the article 17 of the Grant Agreement and EC's Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon Europe and Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon Europe. As it is not considered as a fixed document, updated and more precise versions of the DMP may be delivered at later stages of the project, especially when important changes to the project occur.

It is necessary to mention that the disclosure of the project's data should never jeopardize the project's main objective and the potential protection of generated intellectual property (e.g., patent, product design) and further industrial application. The confidentiality obligations, the security obligations, and the obligations to protect personal data still apply. In case of conflict, the data will not be made openly accessible.

2. Data management in HE Programs

First of all, it seems necessary to remind that a fundamental distinction has to be made, in the frame of Horizon Europe (HE) programs, between peer-reviewed publications, for which open access is an obligation, and open research data, that can be open or closed.

For open research data the commission is running a flexible pilot: Open Research Data pilot that helps HE beneficiaries to make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR), to ensure it is soundly managed.

Initially limited to some research areas, the Open Research Data pilot has been extended since 2017 to cover all the thematic areas of HE. Consequently, it will be applied to SEHRENE project started in 2024.

The aim of ORD pilot is to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data collected/ generated/ processed in the frame of HE projects. Nevertheless, the goal is not to necessarily open all the research data, but rather to follow the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. ORD pilot deals with the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security, as well as data management and preservation issues.

A DMP is a key point to reach the goal of producing FAIR data. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, generated or processed and should include at least information about: (i) how handle research data during and after the end of the project, (ii) what data will be collected, processed, generated, (iii) what data will be opened and what will remain closed and for what reason, (iv) which methodology and standards will be applied, (v) how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

Notice that ORD pilot applies primarily to the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications. Other data can be provided on a voluntary basis as stated in the DMP.

The DMP remain overall a ‘living’ document that has to be kept up to date as the project is running.

A periodical review of the DMP is necessary and has to be defined and discussed between consortium partners.

3. Methodology

3.1 DMP template

In order to assist the beneficiaries with the completion of the DMP, the EC produced and provided a template that acts as a basis for data description. The template contains a set of questions that beneficiaries should answer with a level of detail appropriate to the project. If no related information is available for a given dataset, then the phrase “*Non-applicable*” or N/A will be used. In the following paragraphs, the main sections and proposed contents of the template are listed and presented, along with the way SEHRENE reflects these sections.

3.1.1 Data Summary

In this section, beneficiaries are asked to describe the data by answering the following questions :

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

3.1.2 FAIR Data

3.1.2.1 *Making data findable, including provisions for metadata*

In this section, the Beneficiary shall respond to the following questions:

- Will a persistent identifier identify data?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

3.1.2.2 *Making data accessible*

3.1.2.2.1 Repository:

In this section, the Beneficiary shall respond to the following questions:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

3.1.2.2.2 Data:

In this section, the Beneficiary shall respond to the following questions:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

3.1.2.2.3 Metadata:

In this section, the Beneficiary shall respond to the following questions:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

3.1.2.3 Making data interoperable

In this section, the Beneficiary shall respond to the following questions:

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

3.1.2.4 Increase data re-use

In this section, the Beneficiary shall respond to the following questions:

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

3.1.3 Other research output

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

3.1.4 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

How will long-term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

3.1.5 Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

3.1.6 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

3.1.7 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

3.2 Methodological Steps in SEHRENE

For the 1st version of SEHRENE DMP, the following methodological steps were followed:

1. The coordinator, responsible for the implementation of DMP in the frame of WP1 – Coordination and Management - sent to all partners an email notifying them about the upcoming deliverable. Contribution was asked from all partners that were involved in any data collection in each task of the WPs. They were asked to answer a questionnaire on which data they were expecting to produce and collect during the project.
2. In parallel, the latest guidelines from the EC regarding data management were sent to all partners to be informed.
3. The project team collaborated efficiently and contributed with the needed information.

The first version of the SEHRENE DMP is intended to provide an initial screening of the data to be collected, processed and produced within SEHRENE. It is also the first attempt to collect the vision and input from all the partners involved in any data management option. It can be underlined that not all data generated in SEHRENE will be public for a matter of confidentiality and industrial and intellectual property. A selection of data which can be made available to the community without affecting confidentiality for

partners is provided in below sections. During the upcoming Project Meetings special attention will be given to data management in order to provide further clarifications and conclusions on data management.

4. DMP review timetable

DMP is a living document that can be adjusted all along the project lifetime. Even if no deliverable is planned for the update of the DMP, Partners can request to update the document in accordance with the progress in the project.

At the end of the Project a final Data Management Plan will be available that will detail deeply the SEHRENE project datasets and the way to access to the data.

5. SEHRENE Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan applies to two types of data, as specified in the EC Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon Europe:

1. The data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications.
2. Other data, including associated metadata, as specified in this document.

The types of data that will be generated by SEHRENE are:

1. Data generated during the development (including materials selection & characterization and modelling activities), thermal storage prototype manufacturing and testing results.
2. Data collected from partners through use cases (operating conditions) ; economic, social and technical data collected for Techno-economic analysis, Environmental & LCA, and Social acceptance evaluation.

There will be decisions for each type of data about whether to protect/exploit it, or whether to make it publicly available in publications in accordance with SEHRENE dissemination strategy, or by depositing data without a publication (but only where partners agree this would be a good idea). All partners will receive a prior notice of any planned publication or planned data deposition at least 30 calendar days before the intended date of publication in accordance with Article 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement and Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement.

Figure 1 shows the open access to SEHRENE data in the wider context of dissemination and exploitation.

Figure 1 SEHRENE data in the wider context of dissemination and exploitation

The open SEHRENE data are planned to be deposited and stored on the internal project repository tool (Own Cloud). It has yet to be discussed within the consortium which openly accessible research data repository could be used for depositing the data.

The first draft of the Data Management Plan is shown below where the data and the metadata which will be generated by the consortium are identified. The following information is also provided in the table:

- What methodology and standards will be applied for generating the data.
- How the data will be exploited/made accessible.
- Explanation as to why the data won't be accessible if this is the case.
- How the data will be archived and preserved.
- Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results.

6. Partner's DMP

6.1 CEA's DMP

Table 1. CEA DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP1 collects personal identification information such as the name, surname, email address, name of belonging organisation/company.	Personal data could be collected for newsletters, events (such as Conferences, Workshops and Webinars), etc., during the project lifetime through various channels (e.g. website, sign up forms, emails).	CEA will securely store and keep confidentially the data collected. The computers and servers used to store personal data are located in a secure environment, in particular on the company server, which can only be accessed via a combination of a username and a password. All collected data will only be used within the SEHRENE project and will not be shared with third parties and other projects. The collected data will be stored for the	.xls files with personal identification information such as the name, surname, email address, name of belonging organisation/company.	<p>The personal information will be used to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inform about any changes or updates we make to the services; 2. Alert about relevant opportunities and activities (including project news, results, and event invitations); 3. Provide with other information or services to which people subscribe. <p>The information from the newsletter subscription process is inserted into a programme that manages and sends e-mail. Only emails are used for this purpose. This programme works offline and data is not shared.</p> <p>The information will be used for purposes directly related to the project and will never be shared with third parties (such as marketing companies).</p>	Contact details/data will not be made accessible. Our services, processes and communication systems aim to ensure the highest possible degree of compliance with the applicable law: Regulation (EU) 2016/679, The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).	The personal data will be kept for the minimum period of time necessary for the purposes and/or for compliance with legal obligations. The minimum time required is the duration of the project plus an additional one year (for example: in a 3-year project your data will be kept for 4 years). After this period, data will be removed from the database.	N/A

		remaining project duration.					
WP4 T4.1 PCM selection for the TES	-Data from literature review and internal CEA experiments -Data can be object for scientific publications	Laboratory tests methodology and procedures used in the literature	Evaluation of data from material characterisation measurements. Data table (Excel format) Report (Word format)	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted	Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A
WP4 T4.3 Results of SoC measurement of TES prototype	-Data from literature review and internal CEA experiments -Data can be object for scientific publications and IP	Internal method of CEA	Data table (Excel format) Report (Word format)	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted	Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A
WP4 T4.4 Labscale test of the ETES prototype	-Experimental results from data acquisition system (mainly temperatures, pressures, mass flows...) in text files or csv files. -Data will be useful for who want to assess the thermal performances of such technology or who want to validate their PCM storage model. -Data can be object for scientific publications	Internal method of CEA	Documents that will include sets of parameters of the different experiments, images and tables (Word, Excel)	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted	Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to smart management system will not be made available since this is economically damaging	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A

<p>WP3 T3.3</p> <p>Numerical simulation results</p>	<p>Simulation data from thermal modelling of the TES lattice structure and geometrical definition of the structures itself</p> <p>Data will be usefull for who want to assess the performance of the TES</p> <p>Data can be object for scientific publication</p>	<p>Internal method of CEA</p>	<p>Documents that will include sets of parameters of the different simulation cases, images and tables (Word, Excel)</p>	<p>Supplementary data are available free of charge in all scientific publications. Direct access to data is available in the internal repository.</p>	<p>The models developed during the project are proprietary and will not be delivered with data sets.</p> <p>Only a specific version of the library will make available in open access.</p>	<p>Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist.</p> <p>If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years</p>	<p>N/A</p>
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(*) Metadata can be considered information resources/data about data (i.e. References and information that describes, explains and locates an information resource)

6.2 ULIEGE's DMP

Table 2. ULIEGE DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP3 T3.1 ETES system general design	Simulation data from ETES general design modelling. Data will be useful for who want to understand how to optimize cycle architecture, operating conditions and working fluid. Data can be object for scientific publication.	Internal methods of ULiege, including methodology to develop grey-box models (model construction, calibration and simulation).	Documents that will include sets of parameters of the different simulation cases, images and tables (Word, Excel). Documents that will include sets of inputs conditions for the simulation, especially the requirements for the different use cases (excel, word documents, images).	The models will be disclosed (the sets of equations), but not all specific parameters related to the use cases. General simulation results that can be disclosed will be presented in scientific communication. Other data is available in the project internal repository.	Some specific parameters related to the use cases cannot be disclosed, because they are related to the industrial process.	Internal ULiege database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A
WP3 T3.5 Development of tools for optimal ETES control	Simulation data from ETES dynamic modelling. Data will be useful for who want to understand the benefit of actuators, the benefit of maintaining the system warm to reduce start-up time, and the potential of active charge management when switching from one mode to the other.	Internal methods of ULiege, including methodology to develop dynamic models (model construction, calibration, initialization, and simulation).	Documents that will include sets of parameters of the different simulation cases, images and tables (Word, Excel). Documents that will include sets of inputs conditions for the simulation, especially the requirements for the different use	The models will be disclosed (the sets of equations), but not all specific parameters related to the use cases. General simulation results that can be disclosed will be presented in	Some specific parameters related to the use cases or to specific designs of components (compressor, turbine, heat exchangers) cannot be disclosed, because they are related to the industrial process or because they are	Internal ULiege database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A

	Data can be object for scientific publication.		cases (excel, word documents, images).	scientific communication. Other data is available in the project internal repository.	protected by the manufacturers.		
WP4 T4.4 Labscale test of the 20-kWth heat pump	<p>-Experimental results from data acquisition system (mainly temperatures, pressures, mass flows...) in text files or csv files.</p> <p>-Data will be useful for who want to assess the thermal performances of such technology or who want to validate their hight temperature heat pump model.</p> <p>-Data can be object for scientific publications</p> <p>- Data concern tests conducted at CEA as well as pre-tests conducted in ULiege (before shipping the heat pump to CEA)</p>	Internal methods of ULiege regarding tests definition and post-processing (uncertainty propagation, outliers identification, reconciliation methods, graphical representation)	Documents that will include sets of parameters of the different experiments, images and tables (Word, Excel)	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted	Sensitive data for IPR.	Internal ULiege database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A

6.3 POLIMI's DMP

Table 3. POLIMI DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP3 T3.4 Value set for the thermodynamic properties of points in different plants layouts (look-up tables)	Data provided from previous tasks Data will be useful for who want to assess the performances of ETES systems and / or who want to validate their ETES model.	Selection among data provided in previous tasks according to internal procedure	Data table (Excel format) Report (Word format)	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted Report will be accessible, unless covered by other partner IPR	Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. For data set not covered by IPR: Sehrene open access repository If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A
WP3 T3.4 Energy balances data from simulation of the ETES system; selected Equations of State	Data used and evaluated during simulation by means of Aspen code Data will be useful for those who want to assess the overall performance of ETES systems. Data can be object of scientific publication	Internal procedure	Input and output Aspen file Report (Word format)	Sensitive data because of software license – Direct access to data in Word format available in the internal repository to partner involved in related tasks Report will be accessible, unless covered by other partner IPR	Sensitive data (input and output files) because of software license - will not be made accessible	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. For data set not covered by IPR: Sehrene open access repository If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A

WP5 T5.1 DT description; fundamentals equations and basic assumptions,	Data will be useful for those who want to assess the overall performances of ETES systems. Data can be object of scientific publication	Internal procedure	Report format) (Word	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted Report will be accessible, unless covered by other partner IPR	Sensitive data for IPR.	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. For data set not covered by IPR: Sehrene open access repository If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A
WP5 T5.1 Digital Twin of the ETES system	Set of code modules Data can be object of scientific publication	Code development according to internal procedure	Report format) (Word	Sensitive data for IPR -will not be made accessible	The models developed during the project are proprietary and will not be delivered with data sets.	Local data storage If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A
WP 5 T5.4 Numerical simulation results for techno-economic assessment	Data from coupled utilization of the Digital Twin and the Energy Management System Data will be useful for those who want to assess the economic performances of ETES systems and / or who want to validate their ETES model Data can be object of scientific publication	Code results	Data table (Excel format) Report format) (Word	Direct access to data table is available in the internal repository to partner involved in related tasks Report will be accessible, unless covered by other partner IPR	Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging	Internal CEA database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist. For data set not covered by IPR: Sehrene open access repository If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years	N/A

6.4 TURBODEN's DMP

Table 4. TURBODEN DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP3 T3.2 Components detailed design	Data from WP2 Data can be object for scientific publications	Internal tools and specific design and simulation software.	Detailed design of ORC and HP components Data in excel format Technical specification documents (in word format) PFD process diagrams in PDF format	All information included in the WP3 task (T3.2) are confidential documents and are available only for the members of project consortium	Non-open research data (Turboden know-how on ORC and HP technology)	All data will be stored in internal archive and project documents will be available for partners	Aspen HTFS Autocad
WP3 T3.3 TES detailed design	Data from T3.1, T3.2, T3.4 Data can be object for scientific publications	Turboden gives support to this task answering to specific questions made by partners	Input for supporting TES detailed design (working fluids, design data specifications of ORC, HP) Data in excel format Technical specification documents (in word format)	All information included in the WP3 task (T3.3) are confidential documents and are available only for the members of project consortium	Non-open research data (Turboden know-how on ORC and HP technology)	All data will be stored in internal archive and project documents will be available for partners	N/A

WP3 T3.5 Development of tools for optimal ETES control	Simulation data from TES design and use cases Data can be object for scientific publications--	Internal tools and specific design and simulation software	Control narrative of integrated HP-ETES-ORC control	All information included in the WP3 task (T3.5) are confidential documents and are available only for the members of project consortium	Non-open research data (Turboden know-how on ORC and HP technology)	All data will be stored in internal archive and project documents will be available for partners	N/A
Wp5 T5.4 SEHRENE techno-economic assessment for the use-cases	Techno-economic data for ORC and HP	Internal numerical tools, non-dimensional range of cost diagrams	Technical and economic simulation and assessment for ORC and HP	All information included in the WP5 task (T5.4) are confidential documents and are available only for the members of project consortium	Non-open research data (Turboden know-how on ORC and HP technology)	All data will be stored in internal archive and project documents will be available for partners	N/A

6.5 CIRCE's DMP

Table 5. CIRCE DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP 5- TASK 5.3 DEVELOPMENT OF EMS FOR THE ETES	Numerical data on energy generation, these data will be useful for industries and for the scientific purposes of CIRCE, facilitating studies on prediction models of energy generation and demand. Numerical data on the state of charge of the ETES, data on the need for flexibility in the electrical grid, data on meteorology, and energy prices.	Procedures utilized in literature	Report on the execution of the EMS, according to the user's requests made to us. The format can be an Excel with energy data in kWh, available time in h, cost and benefit in €, and CO ₂ , if requested.	Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted	Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to algorithms, use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging	Internal CIRCE database (tbd) accessible to partners and upon request	Energy Demand data Energy generation data DT data (tbd)

6.6 TORRECID's DMP

Table 6. TORRECID DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP2 T2.1 Information related to industrial site	<p>- Specifications on process of ceramic smelter operation (temperatures, energy consumptions, etc.).</p> <p>-Data will be useful for ETES definition and future implementation.</p>	-Internal data of TOR.	-Data from internal measurements and production control (Word, excel, pdf, etc.)	-Sensitive data from production parameters, blueprints and engineering drawings of smelters will be only accessible to partners.	-Know-how developed internally by TOR without IPR protection.	<p>-Internal TOR database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientist.</p> <p>-If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years</p>	N/A
WP5 T5.2 Information about specific requirements for ETES system	<p>-Technical data about frit melting process (fusing temperature, time, energy consumption, H2 requirement, Hydrogen percentage substitution, hydrogen energy power, fumes temperature, fume flow, PV power energy available for ETES, etc.)</p> <p>-Data will be useful for ETES evaluation and future implementation.</p> <p>-ETES data about implementation in TOR's case (frit smelter).</p>	<p>-Internal data of TOR</p> <p>-ETES will gather data from all partners involved in its implantation in TOR's case.</p>	<p>-Data from internal measurements and production control (Word, excel, pdf, etc.)</p> <p>-Data from all partners involved in ETES implementation.</p>	-Data will be exploited by TOR and rest of partners involved.		<p>-Internal TOR database for exploitation and future implementation.</p>	N/A

<p>WP5 T5.4 Information about optimal operating conditions of ETES from energy and economic perspective.</p>	<p>-ETES data regarding energy and economic assessment about implementation in TOR's case (frit smelter). -ETES data about optimal architecture and specific needs (energy source, heat source, etc.) to minimize LCOS in ceramic frit smelter.</p>	<p>-Internal data about energy and economic assessment from all partners involved in implantation of TOR's ETES case.</p>	<p>-Energy and economic data from TOR and rest of partners involved in ETES implementation for ceramic frit smelter.</p>	<p>-Data will be exploited by all partners involved in implantation of TOR's ETES case. -Data will be accessible for SEHRENE ETES replicability analysis with end-user group and market analysis.</p>		<p>-Internal database accessible for partners involved in energy and economic assessment.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
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6.7 ZORLU's DMP

Table 7. ZORLU DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP2 – T2.1/T2.2 (and related WPs and Tasks that uses the information from WP2)	<p>-Data from Zorlu Enerji geothermal power plants and previous projects.</p> <p>-Data will be useful for creating a system for ETES. It can also be used as a dataset for modelling and publication.</p>	Data will be generated by the means of receiving information from instruments at the power plant.	Documents that contain datasets in Excel form. (or similar)	Some of the data from the site is accessible from publications. Sensitive data will not be shared until IPR protection is made (such as NDA etc.).	Data might include well/plant information that is a trade secret or specifies the exact location of the most efficient reservoir upstream points.	<p>Data will be preserved internally until IPR protection is at place.</p> <p>Zorlu Enerji will also follow grant agreement requirements.</p>	Generic instruments (PIT, TIT and FT) which does not require any specification.
WP6 – T6.1/T6.2/T6.3 (LCA might require plant investment data)	<p>-Data from Zorlu Enerji geothermal power plants and previous projects.</p> <p>-Data will be utilized for LCA generation.</p>	Data is already stored in Zorlu Enerji servers and will be provided when deemed necessary, by the authorisation of Zorlu Enerji.	Documents that contain relevant information such as Word/Excel/PDF (or similar)	Some of the data from the site is accessible from publications. Sensitive data will not be shared until IPR protection is made (such as NDA etc.).	Data might include well/plant information that is a trade secret or specifies the exact location of the most efficient reservoir upstream points.	<p>Data will be preserved internally until IPR protection is at place.</p> <p>Zorlu Enerji will also follow grant agreement requirements</p>	N/A

6.8 CUERVA's DMP

Table 8. CUERVA DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP5 T5.3: Development of the Energy Management System	EMS development in one of the three use-cases of SEHRENE project	Data of Cuerva Living Lab (Smart grid)	Energy power, voltage, current, PV data (power, time between data-data)	tbd	Users data privacy	tbd	N/A

6.9 SPI's DMP

Table 9. SPI DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
<p>WP7 collects personal identification information such as the name, surname, email address, name of belonging organisation/company.</p>	<p>Personal data could be collected for newsletters, events (such as Conferences, Workshops and Webinars), etc., during the project lifetime through various channels (e.g. website, sign up forms, emails).</p>	<p>SPI will securely store and keep confidentially the data collected. The computers and servers used to store personal data are located in a secure environment, in particular on the company server, which can only be accessed via a combination of a username and a password. All collected data will only be used within the SEHRENE project and will not be shared with third parties and other projects. The collected data will be stored for the remaining project duration.</p>	<p>Excel files with personal identification information such as the name, surname, email address, name of belonging organisation/company.</p>	<p>The personal information will be used to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inform about any changes or updates we make to the services; 2. Alert about relevant opportunities and activities (including project news, results, and event invitations); 3. Provide with other information or services to which people subscribe. <p>The information from the newsletter subscription process is inserted into a programme that manages and sends e-mail. Only emails are used for this purpose. This programme works</p>	<p>Contact details/data will not be made accessible. Our services, processes and communication systems aim to ensure the highest possible degree of compliance with the applicable law: Regulation (EU) 2016/679, The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).</p>	<p>The personal data will be kept for the minimum period of time necessary for the purposes and/or for compliance with legal obligations.</p> <p>The minimum time required is the duration of the project plus an additional one year (for example: in a 3-year project your data will be kept for 4 years). After this period, data will be removed from the database.</p>	<p>N/A</p>

				<p>offline and data is not shared.</p> <p>The information will be used for purposes directly related to the project and will never be shared with third parties (such as marketing companies).</p>			
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6.10 TVS's DMP

Table 10. TVS DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP6 T6.1: LCA modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ecoinvent database v3.9 for LCA modelling. - Data from literature review for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) and Levelised Cost of Storage (LCOS) - Data from WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 - Data will be integrated with T6.2 and T6.3 - Data can be object for scientific publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LCA standards ISO 14040, ISO 14044 and ILCD handbook - Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) methodologies: Recipe 2016, IMPACT World+, ILCD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metadata from the design and specification of the materials and components 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitive data for IPR will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted - Only T6.2 and T6.3 will access the data via Application Programming Interface (API) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal TVS database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientists. - If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years 	N/A
WP6 T6.2 Comparative environmental performance evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from T6.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Same as T6.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comparison metadata between State-Of-Art technologies (lead acid and Li-ion batteries) and proposed ETES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted - Only T6.3 will access the data via 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal TVS database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientists. - If applicable: All data will be stored 	N/A

				Application Programming Interface (API)		and archived for 5 years		
WP6 DSS energy storage	T6.3: for	- Data from T6.1 and T6.2	- Same as T6.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Techno economic results - Environmental Impact results - Resource consumption results - LCOS results 	- Sensitive data for IPR-will not be made accessible until IPR protection has been granted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitive data for IPR. Data relating to use cases and/or prototypes will not be made available since this is economically damaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal TVS database accessible to partners and upon request by external scientists. - If applicable: All data will be stored and archived for 5 years 	- User interface from DSS tool

6.11 ULEIC's DMP

Table 11. ULEIC DMP

What data / data set (WP of reference + name) will you generate?	Data set description (its origin, nature, to whom it could be useful, object for scientific publications, existence (or not) of similar data (possibility of integration and reuse)	What methodology and standards will you apply for generating the data?	What metadata (*) will you generate?	How will the data be exploited or made accessible (access procedures, embargo period and identification of the repository)?	Explanation as to why the data will not be accessible	Archiving and preservation (procedures, timing, etc.)	Information on tools and instruments necessary for validating the results
WP3: Task 3.2 and 3.3	Literature data	Collect data from the open literature.	The data will be tabulated and analysed in Excel and Origin, and will be explained in Word.	The data will be made available as per the agreement.	NA	Data produced will be stored on OneDrive and the University's server. Information will also be made public when published in open access via the University's open platform https://figshare.le.ac.uk	NA
WP4: Task 4.2 and 4.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from experiments performed as per task 4.2. - Data can be an object for scientific publications 	The experiments will be performed based on standards given in the literature	The data will be tabulated and analysed in Excel and Origin, and will be explained in Word.	The data which is not confidential will be made available to the public via open-access publications. The data will be shared with the consortium as per the given agreement.	NA	The data produced from the experiments will be stored on OneDrive and the University's server. Information will also be made public when published in open access via the University's open platform https://figshare.le.ac.uk	Thermo-Calc, COMSOL
WP5: Task 5.4: SEHRENE techno-economic assessment for the use cases	Literature data	Collect data from the open literature.	The data will be tabulated and analysed in Excel and Origin, and will be explained in Word.	The data will be made available as per the agreement.	NA	Data produced will be stored on OneDrive and the University's server. Information will also be made public when published in open access via the University's open platform https://figshare.le.ac.uk	NA

7. Degree of progress

The degree of progress for this deliverable is 100%

8. Dissemination level

This Deliverable is PUBLIC, will be published on the project sharepoint and website.